

Classroom aerosol dispersion modeling: experimental assessment of a low-cost flow simulation tool

KEYWORDS: aerosol dispersion; indoor air quality; computational fluid dynamics; CFD; SolidWorks Flow Simulation; STAR-CCM

ABSTRACT:

The purpose of this study was to assess the utility of a low-cost flow simulation tool for an indoor air modeling application by comparing its outputs with the results of a physical experiment, as well as those from a more advanced computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software package. Five aerosol dispersion tests were performed in two different classrooms by releasing a CO₂ tracer gas from six student locations. Resultant steady-state concentrations were monitored at 13 locations around the periphery of the room. Subsequently, the experiments were modeled using both a low-cost tool (SolidWorks Flow Simulation) and a more sophisticated tool (STAR-CCM+). Models were evaluated based on their ability to predict the experimentally measured concentrations at the 13 monitoring locations by calculating four performance parameters commonly used in the evaluation of dispersion models: fractional mean bias (FB), normalized mean-square error (NMSE), fraction of predicted value within a factor of two (FAC2), and normalized absolute difference (NAD). The more sophisticated model performed better in 15 of the 20 possible cases (five tests at four parameters each), with parameters meeting acceptance criteria in 19 of 20 cases. However, the lower-cost tool was only slightly worse, with parameters meeting acceptance criteria in 18 of 20 cases, and it performed better than the other tool in 3 of 20 cases. Because it provides useful results at a fraction of the monetary and training cost and is already widely accessible to many institutions, such a tool may be worthwhile for many indoor aerosol dispersion applications, especially for students or researchers just beginning CFD modeling.

Environmental Significance

The maintenance of healthy indoor air is important to prevent the spread of airborne pathogens and other harmful pollutants. Modeling spaces using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) can be useful for determining the optimal room and ventilation configuration for maximizing occupant health, but such software can be expensive and difficult to learn. A CFD tool that provides reasonably accurate results at significantly lower cost could be useful for many institutions as either an end itself or an initial modeling option.

INTRODUCTION

Maintaining adequate indoor air quality is critical to preventing the spread of infectious aerosols.¹⁻⁴ This is particularly important in shared spaces such as classrooms, wherein students and instructors can be in close proximity for extended periods.⁵⁻⁶ In addition, the maintenance of healthy air could be particularly important to the instructor, who may be in a higher risk category than the students.

Most indoor spaces are not completely well-mixed. It is important to understand the processes of aerosol dispersion within the room because there may be areas of high and low concentration caused by incomplete mixing and the proximity effect.⁷⁻⁸ Such an understanding will enable the optimal design and operation of ventilation and air cleaning devices, as well as the optimal arrangement of the classroom to minimize exposure to both the students and the instructor.

One way to evaluate aerosol dispersion in classrooms is through physical experiments. Although this is time- and labor-intensive, it can yield useful results for specific classroom conditions.⁹⁻¹⁵ Such studies often use aerosol particle generators or CO₂ tracer gas release in conjunction with an array of monitors throughout the room to investigate dispersion, or the effectiveness of air purifier systems. However, the studies are limited because they cannot be quickly repeated to see the effects of changes to boundary conditions, such as ventilation conditions, source location, room geometry, or other factors. Therefore, results are hard to generalize due to the necessarily finite nature of the test.

Modeling through approaches such as computational fluid dynamics (CFD) avoids many of the limitations of the experimental approach. Such models can be manipulated relatively easily to account for a wide variety of conditions. Thus, a number of studies have employed CFD to investigate indoor air quality in classrooms.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ Rencken et al. used CFD to conclude that the well-mixed assumption of rooms results in an underprediction of people's true exposure to infected aerosols.²⁰ In another study, Arjmandi et al. employed CFD modeling to find that having an inlet and outlet ventilation on the floor and ceiling of each student in a classroom was the best method for minimizing transmission because it reduces horizontal air flow contamination.²¹

However, many of these CFD tools tend to be costly in terms of operator training requirements and purchase price. Lower-cost options exist and could provide the benefits of modeling without some of its attendant disadvantages. One such option is SolidWorks Flow Simulation,²² which is a low-cost and readily accessible tool that is widely used and could be potentially useful in classroom aerosol dispersion modeling applications. This software is already widely available to many institutions, and has the ability to both create the model geometry and run the flow simulation in one package. The use of this SolidWorks tool for indoor air quality applications has not been widely documented in the literature. One study by Bustarde et al. used it to optimize the design of an isolation room for COVID-19 patients in the Philippines.²³ Another study by Hirn et al., which was a precursor to the study herein, used the

SolidWorks tool to perform a sensitivity analysis of boundary conditions for a flow simulation model of a classroom.²⁴

Although modeling has the advantage of being precise and repeatable, it is not necessarily accurate. Evaluation of its accuracy relies upon the comparison of model predictions to experimental measurements. With the results of this comparison, performance parameters such as fractional mean bias, normalized mean-square-error, and normalized absolute difference can be employed to evaluate the model and subsequently compared to published acceptance criteria.²⁵⁻²⁶

Several studies have investigated aerosol dispersion in classrooms by comparing experimental and CFD results for a single room. For example, Downing et al.²⁷ verified CFD modeling with measured aerosol concentrations to find the impacts of aerosol recycling, as well as the spatial variability of aerosol concentrations. Duill et al.¹⁴ compared experimental aerosol measurements in several classrooms with a single CFD model of a generic classroom for verification purposes. Finally, Tobisch et al.¹² investigated the utility of an air purifier in a lecture hall using a combination of experimental and CFD results.

The purpose of this study was to assess the utility of a low-cost flow simulation tool for an indoor air application by comparing its outputs with the results of physical experiments, as well as those from a more advanced CFD software. This work is novel in three ways. First, it compares results from indoor air models of classrooms to experimentally measured concentrations across multiple experiments and rooms, resulting in more generalizable results than those from more limited previous studies. Second, this study is the first to apply dispersion model performance parameters to indoor air spaces. Such parameters have been used in the past to assess outdoor models, but never indoor ones; in this work, we show the value of such an application for future modelers. Finally, this study is the first to assess the value of a low-cost and widely available CFD modeling software. If reasonably accurate, such software could serve as a worthy entry point to the field of CFD modeling, potentially resulting in broad increased interest and access to the topical areas of disease transmission and human health.

METHODS

Physical Experiments

For a complete description of the physical experiments, see Dacunto et al. (2022).¹¹ In summary, five CO₂ tracer gas release tests were conducted in two classrooms in different buildings on a university campus in the northeastern United States (Fig. 1). This tracer gas served as a proxy for infectious aerosols,²⁸ which are small enough to follow gas streamlines and stay aloft for extended periods of time. Doors and windows were shut to minimize airflow into and out of the room, and windows were covered to minimize solar influence.

Classroom A (190 m³) contained two 57 cm by 57 cm diffuser-style supply registers in the ceiling, with a 76 cm by 38 cm vent in the lower portion of the door that allowed air to move toward the return in an adjacent hallway. A variable air volume (VAV) box in the ceiling plenum enabled individual control of the supply flow to the room, enabling testing at multiple ventilation

rates (28 and 14 m³ min⁻¹, hereafter referred to as *high flow* and *low flow* for this classroom). Classroom B (180 m³) had four smaller 28 cm by 28 cm supply diffusers in the ceiling, with a 33 cm by 52 cm ceiling return in the corner. Individual control of the supply flowrate of this classroom was not possible, with testing occurring at only 14 m³ min⁻¹.

In each classroom, six student desks were arranged in the middle of the room, each with an associated 1.2 m tall plastic silhouette behind it. The silhouettes were equipped with a lamp and 100 W light bulb to mimic the thermal energy released from a seated student.²⁹ The intent of this setup was to represent the influence of the human form and heat plume on airflow within the room (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 (a)-(b) Experimental configuration and geometry of each classroom, to include monitor locations with reference numbers.

A tracer gas consisting of 25% CO₂ and 75% N₂ by volume was released via 1.3 cm tubing at what mimicked the human mouth of each of the six silhouettes at 29 deg C and 1 m s⁻¹ exit velocity, which is a typical velocity for mouth and nose breathing according to Tang et al.³⁰ This equated to 0.17 g s⁻¹ tracer gas released at each silhouette. Experiments were conducted as

a steady release of tracer gas at either 35 min for the high flow condition in Classroom A, or 55 min for the low flow in Classrooms A and B. This duration was chosen so that there was a 10-min period in which each classroom was at least 95% of the way to steady state, as calculated by a mass balance analysis of each classroom.

The team analyzed CO₂ data from 12 CM-501 handheld multi-gas detectors (CO2Meter.com, Ormond Beach FL USA) around the periphery of the room, placed on survey tripods at 1.5 m (i.e., breathing height). These monitors represented possible locations that an instructor might stand during class. An additional reference monitor (EGM-5 portable gas analyzer, PP Systems, Amesbury MA USA) sampled the classroom return, thus providing data on what was assumed to be the well-mixed portion of the room. Steady-state CO₂ concentrations were calculated at each of the 13 locations as the average of the monitor response during the last 10 min of each test. Background CO₂ concentrations, as measured by a monitor in an adjacent room, were then subtracted from each of these averages to provide a final representative steady-state value for each monitor in each test.

Additional details on testing procedure, instrumentation, data analysis, and uncertainty are in Dacunto et al.¹¹ Notably, 20 tests are described in that reference, but for this study the team used data from only tests 2a, 2b, and 4a in Classroom A, and 1a and 1b for Classroom B. The replicate test 4b in Classroom A was disrupted by a power outage.

Computational Fluid Dynamics Modeling

The team modeled the five experiments in both classrooms using both a low-cost flow simulation tool and a sophisticated CFD software package. Each tool used the same boundary conditions for each room (see Table 1 and Fig. 2), which matched those of the physical experiments. Model room geometry also matched the actual room, except for the ceiling in Classroom A because it was slightly higher in the models than in the physical experiments.

The low-cost tool was SolidWorks Flow Simulation (Dassault Systemes, Waltham MA USA), which is a CFD software embedded within SolidWorks. The SolidWorks software package retails for about \$4000 (USD) for a single user license, and uses a finite volume method with Favre-averaged Navier-Stokes equations and a k- ϵ turbulence model.²² Flow Simulation is able to be run on standard desktop computer systems, and it has numerous capabilities for the visualization of results. SolidWorks software is widely used for a variety of purposes, and thus the Flow Simulation product is reasonably easy to learn, especially for someone already familiar with the design software.

The software includes several pre-set mesh settings from 1 (coarse) to 7 (fine). The team conducted a grid independence study to determine the optimal mesh level; if results were similar after moving to the next finer mesh (e.g., from 2 to 3), the coarser mesh was used (i.e., 2). This resulted in a mesh level of 2 for classroom A (base cell size of 34 cm), and a mesh level of 4 for Classroom B (base cell size of 15 cm). Each classroom included refined mesh in certain areas (e.g., near silhouettes and in corners), resulting in 783,381 cells in Classroom A and 649,105

cells in Classroom B. Simulations were run on a Dell Precision 5820 computer equipped with an Intel Xeon W-2295 3.00 GHz processor and 64 GB of RAM.

To minimize processing time, the model was set to determine steady-state conditions (vs. a transient study), with computations limited to 8 travels. An analysis of the results indicated that this was more than enough to achieve a relatively stable solution. The team established point goals at the location of each monitor, and could thereby extract the average concentration of CO₂ at each location, expressed as a mass fraction above background. This value could then be converted to ppm for comparison to the experimentally measured values, using the following equation, which is based on the ratio of the molecular weight of air to CO₂:

$$ppm = \left(\frac{gCO_2}{gAir} \right) \left(\frac{\frac{29g}{mol} Air}{\frac{44g}{mol} CO_2} \right) 10^6 \quad (1)$$

The team performed a separate flow study of the four-way ceiling diffusers because including this complex local flow in the overall model could create exceedingly long processing times. This was conducted as an external flow analysis of a standard commercial drop ceiling diffuser of appropriate dimensions (e.g., downloaded from McMaster Carr, Princeton, NJ USA),³¹ with outputs of velocities in three dimensions (v_x , v_y , v_z) retrieved from a plane directly below the vents. These velocities served as inputs to the classroom model and were used instead of the supply flow described in Table 1.

The team also modeled the classrooms using STAR-CCM+ (Siemens, Plano TX USA), a more advanced CFD software package that can cost \$30,000 (USD) or more per license.³² In order to take a relatively similar approach as the SolidWorks Flow Simulation, we employed an unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier Stokes model with k- ϵ turbulence. Steady-state average concentrations were calculated from 25–35 min for the high flow test in Classroom A, or 45–55 min for the low flow in Classroom A or the tests in Classroom B.

The contaminate was modeled as a passive scalar that is advected with the flow along with dispersion, which is modeled based on a turbulent Schmidt number of 0.9. The computational mesh of roughly 7 million cells was selected after a mesh independence study was performed that assessed the variation in contaminate concentrations at the monitor locations. Similar to the SolidWorks simulations, a separate simulation of the air inlet diffuser was performed and the velocity profile on the exit plane was stored and used as a boundary condition for the contaminate dispersion simulations in the classroom geometry. Other boundary conditions were set to be consistent with the SolidWorks simulations and experimental measurements. All the simulations were performed on the Hyalite High Performance Computing System, operated and supported by University Information Technology Research Cyberinfrastructure at Montana State University.

Table 1. Classroom Modeling Boundary Conditions. These conditions matched those of the physical experiments.

Boundary Condition Parameter	units	Classroom A (high flow)	Classroom A (low flow)	Classroom B
Tracer emission per source (6)	[g/s]	0.17	0.17	0.17
Tracer gas temp	[C]	29	29	29
Heat flux per student (6)	[W]	100	100	100
Supply air registers	--	2	2	4
Supply Air flow per register	[m ³ /s]	0.22	0.12	0.06
Supply air temp	[C]	20	20	23
Return flowrate	[m ³ /s]	0.43	0.25	0.23
Door crack pressure difference	[Pa]	11	5.5	1.0
Window heat flux	[W/m ²]	75	24 ¹	n/a ²

1. Heat flux was directed out of the room because the windows were cold; this flux was reduced in the low flow experiments in Classroom A because temperatures were not as cold outside during that part of the day. 2. No window heat flux was included in classroom B due to its newer windows and better window coverings.

Fig. 2. Graphic view of classroom geometry and boundary conditions for the CFD models for Classroom A (left) and Classroom B (right).

Calculation of Evaluation Parameters

The performance of each model was assessed using parameters for the evaluation of dispersion models, as cited in Hanna and Chang (2012).²⁶ These parameters compare the model's predicted steady-state concentration at a certain location (C_p) to the experimentally observed steady-state average concentration at the same point (C_o). They include the following (overbars represent an average concentration at the 13 monitoring points):

Fractional mean bias (FB)

$$FB = \frac{2(\overline{C_o - C_p})}{(\overline{C_o + C_p})} \quad (2)$$

Normalized mean-square error (NMSE)

$$NMSE = \frac{\overline{(C_o - C_p)^2}}{(\overline{C_o} \times \overline{C_p})} \quad (3)$$

Fraction of C_p within a factor of two of C_o (FAC2)

$$\text{fraction of 13 total where } 0.5 < \frac{C_p}{C_o} < 2 \quad (4)$$

Normalized absolute difference (NAD)

$$NAD = \frac{\overline{|C_o - C_p|}}{(\overline{C_o + C_p})} \quad (5)$$

The team compared the parameter results to acceptance criteria for rural dispersion models as proposed by Hanna and Chang,²⁶ because these were more stringent than those recommended for the urban models. Acceptance criteria are listed in Table 2 along with the calculated parameters for comparison purposes. Each model had 20 possible parameter calculations (four parameters calculated for each of five experiments).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Observed and predicted concentrations

Observed and predicted concentrations of CO₂ at each of the 13 monitoring locations are shown in the plots of Fig. 3. There is some variability in the results for each classroom and flow condition.

For classroom A in the high flow condition, both models predicted concentrations near the door and at the back of the room reasonably well, with models matching one another at monitors 3–5. However, STAR-CCM+ matched observed concentrations much more closely in the front of the room (8–12). Neither model accurately predicted the low concentrations measured near the window (6 and 7), which was present in tests 2a and 2b. This could indicate either a failure to adequately capture the applicable boundary condition in this area (e.g., a draft that was unaccounted for) or a shortcoming of the models themselves.

In contrast, the low flow condition in classroom A produced model results that were close to one another throughout the room. However, both models considerably overpredicted concentrations on the back and window side (2–6) of the room. Because the lowest observed concentrations were near the window (6), similar to the high flow case, this could be further evidence of shortcomings in the window boundary condition instead of the models themselves.

Classroom B's results were more challenging, wherein observed concentrations varied significantly along the back and door side of the room (1–5) between tests 1a and 1b, though the rest were reasonably close to one another. Results between the models varied significantly in parts of the room as well, with both modeling the results of test 1a better than test 1b. Overall, SolidWorks did a better job of predicting concentrations along the front of the room (7–11), which are the most likely locations for an instructor to stand in this particular room configuration.

Notably, there was more agreement at or near the return (#Rtn, 1, and/or 12) between observed and predicted concentrations than elsewhere in the room. This may be because the monitors at or near the return were sampling the well-mixed portion of the air in the room, as air from throughout the room was swept up into a volume near the return and combined to create a representative average concentration of the room. The models accounted for the mixing that occurred in this area and thus predicted this average concentration more accurately than they could for the concentration in an isolated corner.

In addition, the inability of the models to accurately predict the low concentrations around the windows for all tests in Classroom A, or the low concentration at monitors along the back wall in Test 1b of Classroom B may indicate the importance of accurately capturing boundary conditions. Some condition must have changed in Classroom B between Tests 1a and 1b that the team did not account for in the model; therefore, the results were worse for Test 1b. Obviously, the model's effectiveness will depend upon its inputs.

Fig. 3 (a)-(c) Comparison of experimental and modeled results for classroom A at high flow (top) and low flow (middle), and classroom B (bottom). See Fig. 1 for station locations. There is no data for monitor 1 in Classroom A tests 2a and 2b due to a failure of the instrument during the test.

Model evaluation: performance parameters and acceptance criteria

Dispersion model performance parameters are in Table 2. Overall, both models performed quite well; however, STAR-CCM performed better in 15 of the 20 possible cases, with parameters meeting acceptance criteria in 19 of 20 cases. SolidWorks Flow Simulation was only slightly worse, with parameters meeting acceptance criteria in 18 of 20 cases, and it performed better than the other tool in 3 of 20 cases.

Both models performed the worst across all parameters in Classroom B test 1b, because of the failure to accurately predict concentrations along the back wall in that case, possibly due to some other factor that was not unaccounted for in the room during the experiment. Measured by a count of the most parameters closest to each goal, SolidWorks performed the best in test 4a (Classroom A low flow), whereas STAR-CCM's best performance was determined after test 2b.

Compared to parameters from other dispersion model performance evaluations, the two models herein fared quite well. For example, Hanna and Chang²⁶ used their performance parameters to evaluate models of four major urban tracer release experiments, with FB meeting urban acceptance criteria (which is less stringent than the rural) in only 22 of 60 possible cases, NMSE in 34 of 60, FAC2 in 46 of 60, and NAD in 39 of 60. In another study, predictions from a common regulatory model, AERMOD, were compared to observed concentrations at government monitoring sites at four locations in Nova Scotia, Canada, for PM_{2.5}, NO_x, and SO₂ on an annual, monthly, and hourly basis. In this case the rural acceptance criteria for FB were met 6 of 18 times and 9 of 18 for NMSE and FAC2.³³ The team did not find any studies applying these same criteria to indoor air quality modeling.

Table 2. Model performance parameters. These parameters compare the SolidWorks (SW) and Star-CCM (SCCM) model predictions to experimentally observed concentrations at the 13 monitoring sites within each classroom. Only three calculated parameters fail to meet acceptance criteria, indicated in bold font with an asterisk. Test number designations are from Dacunto et al. (2022).¹¹

	FB ¹		NMSE ²		FAC2 ³		NAD ⁴	
Acceptance criteria	$< 0.30 $		< 3		> 0.5		< 0.3	
Goal (perfect model)	0.0		0.0		1.0		0.0	
model	SW	SCCM	SW	SCCM	SW	SCCM	SW	SCCM
Classroom A (high flow)								
Test 2a	-0.35*	-0.18	0.15	0.05	0.92	1.0	0.17	0.09
Test 2b	-0.26	-0.08	0.09	0.03	1.0	1.0	0.13	0.06
Classroom A (low flow)								
Test 4a	-0.20	-0.17	0.08	0.07	1.0	1.0	0.12	0.11
Classroom B (low flow)								
Test 1a	-0.26	-0.22	0.10	0.14	1.0	0.92	0.14	0.15
Test 1b	-0.51*	-0.47*	0.34	0.27	0.69	0.85	0.25	0.24

¹FB = Fractional Mean Bias; ²NMSE = Normalized Mean Squared Error; ³FAC2 = Fraction of C_p within a factor of Two of C_0 ; ⁴NAD = Normalized Absolute Difference

Comparison of the two models

Although Star-CCM+ produced better results overall, they were only slightly superior to those from SolidWorks, which can cost roughly \$25,000 (USD) less per license. In many cases, it may be sufficient to use the lower-cost tool to model a space, either as an initial tool to test various configurations before doing more intensive CFD modeling or as an end in itself. Since many institutions may already have SolidWorks with the Flow Simulation package along with trained operators, this low barrier to entry confers it as a significant advantage.

In addition, the software includes the ability to build the geometry of the space to be modeled, something STAR-CCM+ must import from other programs. This simplifies the workflow, given that the same package can create the geometry and perform the simulation, and provides it another advantage over more sophisticated software tools. SolidWorks Flow Simulation also includes many fully integrated visualization tools that can be used to further understand dispersion processes at work. For example, the simple cut plots in Fig. 4 show how the heat plumes from students force CO₂ tracer toward the ceiling, and that the area near the door in classroom A has a lower concentration than the front at the seated student breathing height.

In addition, Flow Simulation's ease of use enables rapid examination of a variety of conditions, such as the impact of opening a door or window. Model results from three different scenarios in Classroom B are also shown in Fig. 4: the base case that matched the experimental setup and the impacts of opening a single door or window. These openings were simulated by adding a boundary condition of a 0.5 Pa pressure difference to the area of the opening.

The open door had a huge effect because it lowered tracer gas concentrations significantly throughout the room, except in the very center section where the emissions were actively occurring. The model results indicate that opening one door would have far-reaching effects, especially for an instructor. Reductions in tracer gas concentrations were not as significant throughout the room after opening a single window, but this action did have a positive impact on the exposure of students in the back row. However, the team acknowledges that, in certain cases, this may actually increase exposure to students who are far from the window, as described by Rencken et al.²⁰

These are just two examples of how a low-cost CFD model could be useful for quickly investigating the impact of changes to room geometry or boundary conditions on exposure to infectious aerosols, or other hazardous gases. The model could be used to quickly iterate on a wide variety of setups, with a more sophisticated and computationally intensive model being employed only on the most promising candidates.

Fig. 4 Mass fraction of CO₂ as modeled by SolidWorks Flow Simulation for experimental base case in Classroom A (upper left panel) and B (upper right panel). An examination of the impact of an open door or window in classroom B is in the two lower panels.

Limitations

This study included only two rooms and two flow conditions, and thus the team acknowledges that results could vary with a larger sample. Nevertheless, the geometry and HVAC systems did vary enough between the two rooms that the results regarding the usefulness of the low-cost model are not unique to a single room.

In addition, both the modeling and experimental work relies on the assumption that the CO₂ tracer gas serves as a good proxy for infectious aerosols; although this is generally true because of the aerosols' small size and ability to follow streamlines, the work would not apply to larger particles generated from sneezing or coughing, or to other types of particles (e.g., dust from sweeping or sanding, other gases, etc.).

Finally, by design, the study used a limited number of boundary conditions to simplify the modeling. A more accurate result could be obtained by better assessing experimental room conditions (e.g., possible window drafts in classroom A) and including these as additional model boundary conditions.

CONCLUSION

In this study the team demonstrated the utility of a low-cost flow simulation tool, SolidWorks Flow Simulation, for an indoor air application by evaluating its performance against results from physical experiments, and those from a more expensive CFD software package. Given that the low-cost tool met acceptance criteria in 18 of 20 cases and its results were only marginally worse than those from the more sophisticated CFD software, its benefits seem to exceed the significantly lower cost in terms of purchase price, accessibility, and operator training. Such a tool is already widely available and could be particularly useful as an initial modeling option to screen through several possibilities, with only the most promising moving on to a more comprehensive CFD software. As such, with its low barrier to entry it could be particularly useful to students or junior researchers who are interested in simple CFD modeling. Additional studies comparing results from experiments in other rooms would be useful to further generalize these results.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts to declare.

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